

KASR TARTIBLI DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALARGA QO'YILADIGAN BOSHLANG'ICH MASALALAR UCHUN VARIATSION ITERATSION USUL

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Annotation: We apply the variational iteration method for solving linear and nonlinear fractional differential equations with the initial conditions. In this method, the problems are initially approximated with possible unknowns. Then a correction functional is constructed by a general Lagrange multiplier, which can be identified optimally via the variational theory. Being different from the other non-linear analytical methods, such as perturbation methods, this method does not depend on small parameters, such that it can find wide application in non-linear problems without linearization or small perturbations.

Keywords: Caputo fractional differential derivative and integral, variational iteration method, Lagrange multiplier, Laplace transform.

Annotatsiya: Chiziqli va chiziqli bo'lmagan kasrli differensial tenglamalarni dastlabki shartlar bilan yechish uchun variatsion iteratsiya usulini qo'llaymiz. Ushbu usulda muammolar dastlab mumkin bo'lgan noma'lumlar bilan yaqinlashadi. Keyin tuzatish funktsiyasi umumiy Lagrange multiplikatori tomonidan tuziladi, uni variatsion nazariya orqali optimal tarzda aniqlash mumkin. Boshqa chiziqli bo'lmagan analitik usullardan, masalan, tebranish usullaridan farqli bo'lgan holda, bu usul kichik parametrlarga bog'liq emas, shuning uchun u chiziqli bo'lmagan yoki kichik tebranishlarsiz chiziqli bo'lmagan masalalarda keng qo'llanilishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Kaputo kasr tartibli hosila va integral, variatsion iteratsion metod, Lagrangch ko'paytuvchisi, Laplas almashtirishi.

Hozirgi vaqtda ko'plab tadqiqotchilar tomonidan qo'llaniladigan variatsion iteratsiya usuli chiziqli yoki chiziqli bo'lmagan differensial tenglamalarning katta sinfini boshqarishga qodir. Usul tomonidan taqdim etilgan moslashuvchanlik va moslashuv uni amaliy fanlar va muhandislik sohasida bo'lgani kabi, yechim oldindan noma'lum bo'lgan holatlarda ham osonlik bilan qo'llash imkonini berdi. variatsion iteratsion metod fanlardagi real dunyo ilovalari uchun analitik taxminiy yechimlar va raqamli simulyatsiyalar uchun samarali algoritmi taqdim etadi. Nochiziqli atamalar bilan ishlash uchun hisoblash algoritmlari odatda qo'llaniladigan Adomian parchalanish usulidan farqli o'laroq, variatsion iteratsion metod chiziqli bo'lmagan atamalar uchun analitik hisoblarni murakkablashtiradigan cheklovchi taxminlardan

foydalanishni talab qilmaydi. variatsion iteratsion metod chiziqli va chiziqli bo'lmagan masalalarga xuddi shunday tarzda yondashadi.

Ushbu ishning asosiy ikki maqsadi bor. Birinchidan, biz variatsion iteratsion metodni turli xil tartibdagi o'zgaruvchan koeffitsientli chiziqli va chiziqli bo'lmagan kasr tartibli differensial tenglamalarga birlashtirilgan tarzda qo'llashni maqsad qilganmiz. Ikkinchidan, biz ilmiy muammolarni hal qilishda usulning ishonchligini tasdiqlashni maqsad qilganmiz, ya'ni gibril tanlash modeli, biz faqat usulning asosiy bosqichlarini taqdim etamiz.

Aytaylik $\alpha > 0$ va $n = \alpha$ bo'lsin. Kaputo α kasr tartibli hosila quyidagicha ta'riflanadi:

$${}^C D_t^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \int_a^t (t-u)^{n-\alpha-1} \left(\frac{d}{du} \right)^n f(u) du$$

$a = 0$ uchun, quyidagicha belgilash kiritamiz:

$${}^C D_t^\alpha f(t) = D^\alpha f(t).$$

Endi esa chiziqsiz kasr tartibli differensial tenglamani yechish uchun variatsional iteratsion metod bilan tanishamiz. Quyidagi kasr tartibli differensial tenglamani ko'rib chiqaylik:

$$D^\alpha y(t) + R[y(t)] + N[y(t)] = g(t),$$

bu yerda $g(t)$ berilgan funksiya, $N[y(t)]$ chiziqsiz operator va R qoldiq chiziqli operator. Tenglama quyidagi boshlang'ich shartlar bilan berilgan bo'lsin:

$$y^{(k)}(0) = y_0^{(k)}, \quad m-1 < \alpha \leq [\alpha] = m, \quad k = 0, \dots, m-1,$$

mavjudlik va yagonalik shartlarini qanoatlantiradi deb hisoblaymiz.

Laplas almashtirish metodini qo'llaymiz:

$$L[y(t)] = Y(s) = Y,$$

$$L[D^\alpha y(t)] = s^\alpha Y - \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} y_0^{(k)} s^{\alpha-k-1}.$$

Quyidagi rekkurent ko'rinishda yozilgan korreksion moslik bilan tanishamiz:

$$Y_{n+1} = Y_n + \lambda(s) \left[s^\alpha Y_n - \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} y_0^{(k)} s^{\alpha-k-1} + L[R[y_n]] + N[y_n] - g(t) \right],$$

bu yerda $\lambda(s)$ Lagranj ko'paytuvchisi.

$\frac{\delta Y_{n+1}}{\delta Y_n} = 0$ shart qo'yamiz. Va quyidagiga kelamiz:

$$1 + \lambda(s) s^\alpha = 0 \Rightarrow \lambda(s) = -\frac{1}{s^\alpha}.$$

Natijada:

$$Y_{n+1} = \frac{1}{s^\alpha} \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} y_0^{(k)} s^{\alpha-k-1} - \frac{1}{s^\alpha} L[R[y_n] + N[y_n] - g(t)]$$

yoki

$$y_{n+1}(t) = L^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^\alpha} \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} y_0^{(k)} s^{\alpha-k-1} - \frac{1}{s^\alpha} L[R[y_n] + N[y_n] - g(t)] \right].$$

$$y(t) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_n$$

1-misol. Quyidagi kasr tartibli differensial tenglamani yechish uchun variatsion iteratsion metodidan foydalaning:

$$D^\alpha y(t) = 1 + \int_0^t y(u) du,$$

boshlang'ich shart bilan berilgan:

$$y(0) = 1, \quad 0 < \alpha \leq 1.$$

Yechim. Laplas almashtirishidan foydalanib ketma-ket quyidagilarga ega bo'lamiz:

$$L[y(t)] = Y,$$

$$s^\alpha Y - s^{\alpha-1} = \frac{1}{s} + L \left[\int_0^t y(u) du \right],$$

$$Y_{n+1} = Y_n + \lambda(s) \left[s^\alpha Y_n - s^{\alpha-1} - \frac{1}{s} - L \left[\int_0^t y(u) du \right] \right],$$

$$\frac{\delta Y_{n+1}}{\delta Y_n} = 0 \Rightarrow 1 + \lambda(s) s^\alpha = 0 \Rightarrow \lambda(s) = -\frac{1}{s^\alpha},$$

$$y_{n+1} = L^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{s^{\alpha+1}} + \frac{1}{s^\alpha} L \left[\int_0^t y(u) du \right] \right],$$

$$y_n(t) = 1 + \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + L^{-1} \left[\frac{Y_n}{s^{\alpha+1}} \right],$$

$$y_1 = 1 + \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \frac{t^{\alpha+1}}{\Gamma(\alpha+2)},$$

...

$$y(t) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_n$$

2-misol. VARIATSION ITERATSION METOD dan foydalanib quyidagi shartlar bilan berilgan kasr tartibli differensial tenglamani yeching:

$$D^\alpha y(t) = 1 + \int_0^t (t-u) y(u) du,$$

$$y(0) = 1, \quad y'(0) = 0, \quad 1 < \alpha \leq 2.$$

Yechish. Laplas almashtirishidan foydalanib quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$L[y(t)] = Y,$$

$$s^\alpha Y - s^{\alpha-1} = \frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{s^2} L[y_n(u)],$$

$$\frac{\delta Y_{n+1}}{\delta Y_n} = 0 \Rightarrow 1 + \lambda(s) s^\alpha = 0 \Rightarrow \lambda(s) = -\frac{1}{s^\alpha},$$

$$y_{n+1} = L^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s} + \frac{1}{s^{\alpha+1}} + \frac{1}{s^{\alpha+2}} L[y_n] \right],$$

$$y_n(t) = 1 + \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + L^{-1} \left[\frac{Y_n}{s^{\alpha+2}} \right],$$

$$y_0 = 1,$$

$$y_1 = 1 + \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} + \frac{t^{\alpha+2}}{\Gamma(\alpha+3)},$$

...

$$y(t) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_n$$

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